

Consumer Practices in Rizal Nueva Ecija: A Basis for Adopting an Effective Marketing Strategy for Micro Small and Medium Enterprises

Authors' Details:

⁽¹⁾**Isagani Facun Pascua**, MBA-Faculty Member, College of Management and Business Technology (CMBT) Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology, Atate Campus, Philippines
isagani_16@rocketmail.com

Rowell Agliones Diaz, MBA, Ph.D(©)-Faculty Member, College of Management and Business Technology (CMBT) Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology-San Isidro Campus, Philippines
wellro0917@gmail.co

Abstract

It is stated that marketing is a never ending activity. All marketing revolve around the consumer. For this reason, there is constant need to study, analyse and understand the consumer, his needs, wants, taste, preferences, biases, practices and many others. It is the responsibility of the retailer or seller to fully evaluate and understood these factors as it affects the daily operation of the business. The retailer or seller must be able to identify as to what products consumer needs, when and how they buy these products, where they buy the products and their capacity of consumer to obtain these products.

The study will focus on how consumers will buy products, how price and promotion will affect their buying, what is the buying time and where will they buy. Since the research is concerned with the existing consumer practices in Rizal, Nueva Ecija, descriptive method is the most appropriate method to be used. Descriptive research method was utilized in this study. A total of 351 respondents were selected out of 2,921 household in selected barangay in the Municipality of Rizal using Pearson Product Moment Correlation and One Way ANOVA as statistical tools. The output of the study revealed that the respondents' profile, monthly income, has no correlation to the respondents' consumer practices. This leads to the acceptance of the null hypothesis. The findings show that there is a statistical proof that there exists no significant relationship between the respondents' profile, monthly income and their consumer practices and three (3) out of six consumer practices have significant difference. These are: Product Bought; Prices of Product; and Store Reputation. The table above further shows that that there is a significant difference on the factor that influences them to buy or shop in retail store.

Keywords: Consumer Practices, Marketing Strategy, MSMEs, Consumer, Marketing Mix, Product, Rizal, Nueva Ecija

INTRODUCTION

The act of obtaining a desired product or service by an individual or group of individuals by offering something in return takes place in the so called market. This is where buyers and sellers interact with each other in exchange of goods and services that will satisfy both their needs and goals. Market as it is known, is a mechanism that facilitates the forces of supply and demand; it is a place where exchanges of goods and services take place. Thus, it is where the buyers buy and the sellers' sells commodities.

According to Go, (2001) "Marketing is the interfacing of a company and its target market". Like any other businesses small scale enterprises, specifically retailers must be able to adopt an effective marketing strategy in selling their products or services. Businesses must analyze the different consumer practices of their target market. In doing so, they will be able to know what are the needs and wants of the consumer.

Rizal, 4th class municipalities, where people are agriculture dependent, small scale enterprises like groceries increases rapidly. Nowadays, due to the flourishing number of similar stores, retailers are trying to stand out their performances among others at all time. In Rizal, Nueva Ecija alone, there are lots of stores that exist and all of them compete with one another to have sales to gain profit. In doing so, these stores study and evaluate consumer practices. This is a requirement in order for them to achieve its goals, to have sales. Indeed, knowledge about consumer practices not only assures the business to maximize its sales that will lead to the attainment of its goals and objectives, but also to satisfy consumer needs and wants. Similarly,

consumers in Rizal still buy their necessities in other places due to differences in price, product availability, store reputation and other reasons.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

This study entitled “Consumer Practices in Rizal, Nueva Ecija: A Basis for Adopting an Effective Marketing Strategy for Small Scale Enterprises”, it sought to determine the profile of the consumer respondents be described in terms of age, sex, civil status, educational attainment and monthly income; the consumer practices in Rizal, Nueva Ecija be described in terms of products bought, prices of products, promotions, time of purchase, store location and store reputation; factors influencing consumer practices in Rizal, Nueva Ecija in terms of Product, Price, Promotion and Location; Is there a significant relationship between profiles of the respondents and their consumer practices? And Is there a significant difference among the respondents’ consumer practices of the six (6) barangays in Rizal, Nueva Ecija?

METHODOLOGY

The study will focus on how consumers will buy products, how price and promotion will affect their buying, what is the buying time and where will they buy. Since the research is concerned with the existing consumer practices in Rizal, Nueva Ecija, descriptive method is the most appropriate method to be used. The descriptive method was employed in conducting the study. Best and Khan (1998) defines a descriptive study as one which describes and interprets what it is. It is concerned with conditions or relationships that exist, opinions that are held, processes that are going on, effects that are evident, or trends that are developing.

Rizal is a 3rd class municipality situated in an agricultural land near mountainous area of Nueva, Ecija. According to the latest census, it has a population of 52,465 people in 10,001 households. Adjacent to the busy town are the six barangays namely: Poblacion East, Poblacion West, Poblacion Centro, Poblacion Sur, Poblacion Norte and Calaoacan which composes 2,921 households. Thus, this is where the study takes place. Respondents were the people residing in the six (6) barangays adjacent to the public market. Out of 2,921 households 351 were selected as sample.

Questionnaire is divided into two parts. The first part is the Consumer profile and the second, the practices of the consumers. Part 2 is the Factors affecting consumer practices which are sub-divided into two parts. The first part of Part 2 is composed of 6 sub-parts. Part 1 is composed of 6 items which is designed to find out the considerations of consumer when it comes to product bought. Part 2 is composed of 5 items which is designed to find out the consumer practices considering the prices of the product. Part 3 is composed of 5 items which is designed to find out the effect of Promotion to consumer practices. Part 4 is composed of 7 items which is designed to find out the time of purchase of the consumers. Part 5 is composed of 6 items which is designed to find out the store location which the respondents buy their needed products. Part 6 is composed of 8 items which is designed to find out why consumers patronize a particular store. The second part of part 2 is the factors that influence the consumers in buying product with considerations of; product, price, location, promotion.

To determine the verbal interpretation, the following range was used.

Degree of Response	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50- 5.0	Always
4	3.50- 4.49	Very Often
3	2.50-3.49	Often
2	1.50- 2.49	Sometimes
1	1.49 and below	Never
Degree of Response	Range	Verbal Interpretation
5	4.50- 5.0	Always Influence
4	3.50- 4.49	Very Often Influence

3	2.50-3.49	Often Influence
2	1.50- 2.49	Sometimes Influence
1	1.49 and below	Never Influence

Ranking was finally used to prioritize the degree of response as they have been consolidated. To answer the hypothesis “There is no significant relationship between the profiles and their consumer practices”, Pearson Product Moment Coefficient Correlation was used. To answer the hypothesis “There is no significant difference among the respondents’ consumer practices of the six barangays in Rizal, Nueva Ecija”, the one way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was used.

RESULTS

This portion discusses the results of findings of the study;

Summary of the Respondents Profile

Age			
	Frequency	Percent	Rank
16-26	55	15.67	3
27-37	116	33.05	2
38-48	117	33.33	1
49-59	53	15.10	4
60 and above	10	2.85	5
Gender			
Male	66	18.80	2
Female	285	81.20	1
Civil Status			
Single	57	16.24	2
Married	282	80.34	1
Widowed	12	3.42	3
Educational Attainment			
Elementary Graduate	39	11.11	3
High School Graduate	171	48.72	1
College Graduate	137	39.03	2
Masters Degree	2	0.57	4.5
Doctors Degree	2	0.57	4.5
Monthly Income			
1,500-7,500	209	59.54	1
8,000-13,500	111	31.62	2
14,000-19,500	23	6.55	3
20,000-25,500	3	0.85	5
26,000 above	5	1.42	4

This table shows that majority of the respondents belonged to age bracket 28-38, female respondents dominated the male respondents. Most female are the one’s who left at home to perform household chores, majority of the respondents were married. Most of them are at the precious moment enjoying the life of having a family and majority of the respondents are High School Graduate. Most of the respondents after graduation in High School have established their own family, majority of the respondents are receiving or earning an income of 1,500-7,500 a month, most of them are farmers and owners of small business, majority of the consumer practices were rated “very often” by the respondents.

Evaluation and monitoring is a part purchase buying process. That Product and Price “very often” influence consumer to buy or shop in a retail store. That there is no correlation between the respondents’ profile and consumer practices. The null hypothesis, there is no significant relationship between respondents’ profile and consumer practices is accepted. There is significant difference on four (4) consumer practices. There significant difference on three (3) consumer practices.

Consumer Practices and Factors	DF	F	F-critical	Interpretation
Product Bought	5/346	6.647088	2.240076	Significant
Prices of Product	5/346	5.073247	2.240076	Significant
Promotion of Product	5/346	1.791467	2.240076	Not significant
Time of Purchase	5/346	2.029918	2.240076	Not significant
Store Location	5/346	1.523795	2.240076	Not significant
Store Reputation	5/346	7.663937	2.240076	Significant
Factors	5/346	4.328192	2.24007	Significant

RECOMENDATION

Retail stores in Rizal should always evaluate and study the pattern of changes in consumer practices to keep them updated as to what, when, where, and how consumers buy their needed products. Retail stores should strengthen their marketing strategy to establish a good relationship to consumers. Thus, creating a loyalty to the store is recommended. Retail stores should adapt a marketing strategy to persuade consumer who shop or buy products in other places. Continuous evaluation of the consumer practices is a must for retail stores to cater them as their needs arise. Retail store should devise a marketing strategy that will effectively influence consumer buying behavior.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

The researcher would like to extend his sincerest appreciation and gratitude to the people / individuals who have extended their generous support and assistance for the successful completion of this study:

References

- i. *Aslina Saad, Jamilah Hamid dan Sairabanu Omar Khan(2005), "CSCW: Konsep dan Aplikasi Kolaborasi dalam Bidang Pendidikan Menerusi Portal." Seminar Penyelidikan Pendidikan MPBL 2005. 15-16 September 2005. Holiday Inn Kuching, Sarawak. Dicapai dari <http://www.ipbl.edu.my/inter/penyelidikan/seminarpapers/2005/index.cfm>*
- ii. *Berhannudin Mohd Salleh (2006) "Use of an Online Forum to Promote Usage of English Language Among Engineering Undergraduates". A Doctoral Thesis submitted at Universiti Teknologi Malaysia.*
- iii. *Bartha, Z., S Gubik, A., & Bereczk, A. (2019). The Social Dimension of the Entrepreneurial Motivation in the Central and Eastern European Countries. Entrepreneurial Business and Economics Review, 7(1), 9-27.*
- iv. *Biraglia, A., & Kadile, V. (2017). The role of entrepreneurial passion and creativity in developing entrepreneurial intentions: Insights from American homebrewers. Journal of Small Business Management, 55(1), 170-188.*
- v. *Cho, Y. H., & Lee, J. H. (2018). Entrepreneurial orientation, entrepreneurial education and performance. Asia Pacific Journal of Innovation and Entrepreneurship, 12(2), 124-134.*
- vi. *Chou, C. M., Shen, C. H., Hsiao, H. C., & Chen, S. C. (2017). Tertiary students' entrepreneurial career intentions of entrepreneurship-embedded internship programs. Studies in Higher Education, 42(11), 2116-2133.*
- vii. *Dendup, T., & Acharja, I. L. (2017). Effect of individual factor on entrepreneurship intention among undergraduate students in Bhutan. World Journal of Business and Management, 3(2), 1-12.*
- viii. *Do, B. R., & Dadvari, A. (2017). The influence of the dark triad on the relationship between entrepreneurial attitude orientation and entrepreneurial intention: A study among students in Taiwan University. Asia Pacific Management Review, 22(4), 185-191.*
- ix. *Dzomonda, O., Fatoki, O., & Oni, O. (2017). The impact of leadership styles on the entrepreneurial orientation of small and medium enterprises in South Africa. Journal of Economics and Behavioral Studies, 9(2), 104-113.*

Authors Profile

ISAGANI FACUN PASCUA, MBA, received the Masters degree in Business Administration (MBA) from Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology and BS degree in Business Administration major in Entrepreneurship at NEUST. During November 20112, he worked as OIC and Faculty Member in one of the TechVoc School in Nueva Ecija and now, he is currently working as Full time Faculty Member in the College of Management and Business Technology at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology – Atate Campus.

ROWELL AGLIONES DIAZ, MBA, currently in the candidate status for the post graduate degree in Doctor of Philosophy with area of specialization in Business Administration. He received the Masters degree in Business Administration (MBA) from Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology and BS degree in Accountancy at MV Gallego Foundation Colleges. He worked at FG Valino Accounting Firm as Head / Supervisor of Financial and Audit Department. He also worked in various private and public institutions as Auditor, Management Consultant, Researcher and Resource Speaker and now, he is currently working as Full time Faculty Member in the College of Management and Business Technology at Nueva Ecija University of Science and Technology – San Isidro Campus where he also serving as President of Faculty and Employees Club and Student Council Adviser .